

PAM 43.660 frag. 81 (IAA Plate 92, frag. 63) a 4Q319 (4QOtot) Fragment

Eibert Tigchelaar

KU Leuven, 13 December 2021

The hitherto unidentified Dead Sea Scrolls Qumran Cave 4 fragment PAM 43.660 frag. 81 (IAA Plate 92, frag. 63) can easily be identified as belonging to 4Q319 (4QOtot) on the basis of the new photograph by Shai Halevi on the Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library. It reads שכני]ה in its first line (only part of the *yod* preserved), and has a few unidentifiable traces of the tops of letters in the second line. The hand of the writing is the same as that of 4Q319, and the dark colour and the horizontal breaks are typical of the remnants of that manuscript. The name שכני]ה occurs very frequently in 4Q319, but I have not found a material join with any of the other 4Q319 fragments.

Image from <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-502377>
Photo Shai HaLevi

- | | |
|-----------------------|---|
| PAM 43.660 | Dana M. Pike and Andrew C. Skinner, <i>Qumran Cave 4 XXIII Unidentified Fragments</i> , Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XXXIII (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001), Pl. I
https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285439 |
| IAA Plate 92 | https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-508196 |
| IAA Plate 92 frag. 63 | https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-502377 (infrared);
https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-502376 (colour) |
| 4Q319 | See Shemaryahu Talmon, Jonathan Ben Dov, Uwe Glessmer, <i>Qumran Cave 4 XVI Calendrical Texts</i> , Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XXI (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001), 194-244 |